

Quality Control Analysis of Cinspere CH-20 Production Using the CUSUM-EWMA Control Chart in PT. XYZ

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Abstract

PT. XYZ is a manufacturing company specializing in textile auxiliaries. In the manufacturing industry, quality is the most important thing. Therefore PT. XYZ continues to improve quality by using control charts. This research uses a Cumulative Sum (CUSUM) control chart and an Exponentially Weighted Moving Average (EWMA) control chart and compares their performance in detecting shifts in production data. This research uses two parameters, namely viscosity and dry matter, to determine Cinsperse CH-20 production is statistically controlled. The research started by analyzing the CUSUM control chart and EWMA control chart on viscosity and dry matter parameters. The analysis is carried out by calculating statistic values, the control limit, and forming each control chart. Next, the Average Run Length (ARL)'s value will be calculated to compare the performance of the two control charts. Based on the application results, Cinsperse CH-20 production at PT. XYZ, the viscosity of CUSUM and EWMA control chart have one plot point outside the control limit. However, the CUSUM and EWMA dry meter control charts have no plots outside the control limit. Based on the ARL value, the value of the ARL control chart known for the viscosity parameter gets results 79,542 for CUSUM and 51,5460 for EWMA, while the dry matter parameter gets 135,5638 for CUSUM and 82,2186 for EWMA. Based on the analysis result, the conclusion is the viscosity parameter is statistically uncontrolled while the parameter of dry matter is controlled by the statistic, and the results of ARL calculation conclusion is both parameters itself show that the EWMA control chart is more sensitive than the CUSUM control chart in detecting a mean shift which more relatively small in Cinsperse CH-20 production at PT. XYZ.

Keywords: SPC, Control Chart, CUSUM, EWMA, ARL.

INTRODUCTION

PT. XYZ is a manufacturing company in the auxiliaries field for textile which is located in Banjaran, Bandung. PT XYZ produces various textile chemical additives for sizing, pretreatment, dyeing, and finishing processes. PT. XYZ has a Cinsperse CH-20 product that often gets mixed results. It is caused by unsuitable conditions and handling at production time. The monomer and catalyst dosing process being too fast will cause the product to become too liquid, while the monomer and catalyst feeding process for too long will cause the product to become thick. This research is based on these varied results and aims to determine Cinsperse CH-20 production is statistically controlled.

In general, the control chart often being used in quality control is the Shewhart control chart. But unfortunately, it's less sensitive to small shifts so that other control charts appear to become an alternative, such as Cumulative Sum (CUSUM) and Exponentially Weighted Moving Average (EWMA) (Hakam, 2017).

In research (Hidayah, 2010), the results show that the mean shifts between 1.0σ to 1.5σ control chart that is effective and provides the best performance is the CUSUM control chart. As for the mean shifts less than 1.0σ , the EWMA control chart shows better detection than CUSUM.

Next, on the research (Han, et al 2010), the results are in comparisons between CUSUM and EWMA, the CUSUM charts were superior in dealing with a large shift with a later change in time. However, the EWMA charts outperformed the CUSUM charts in situations with a small shift and an early change in time.

And the last in research (Vera do Carmo, et al 2004), the results were observed that the CUSUM control chart practically did not sign points out of control for the levels of variation between ± 1.0 standard deviation. For this variant level, the EWMA control chart is more efficient than CUSUM. Among the parameters of the EWMA control chart, with constants = 0,10 and 0,05, with control limit, $L = 2,814$ and $2,625$ respectively, is the one who detects the number of positions that change into the larger one.

Because of that, in this research, the statistical process control (SPC) was carried out to detect small changes in the product results to improve the quality of the product if the product result is outside the control limit, it will declare as a defect because the product results become harder if it passes the upper control limit and softer if it passes the lower

control limit. The statistical quality control here to control products in the production process, Cinsperse CH-20 presents the utilization of Cumulative-Sum (CUSUM) control chart, and Exponentially Weighted Moving Average (EWMA) control chart. By use the parameters k and h on the CUSUM control chart are $k = 0,5$ and $h = 4$ and the weighting factor on the EWMA control chart $\lambda = 0,05$ and $L = 2,615$ (Montgomery D. , 2013).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Quality Control

Quality is a suitability with required specifications (Crosby, 1979). Quality shared into five categories, the main approaches to the definition of quality can be identified: (Garvin, 1984)

1. The transcendent philosophy approach.
2. The economic approach is based on product.
3. The economic, marketing, and operations management approach that based on the user.
4. The manufacturing-based approach.
5. The operations management approach that based on value.

Statistical Quality Control

Statistical quality control is quality supervision, an effort to maintain the quality or quality of the goods produced to comply with the standard of product specifications (Assauri, 1998). The main objective of statistical quality control is to reduce systemic variability in the product's key characteristics (Montgomery D. C., 2009).

Kolmogorov Smirnov Normality Test

A normality test is a test carried out intending to assess the distribution of data in a group of data or variables, whether the distribution of the data is being normally distributed or not. Testing the normality of the data can use Kolmogorov Smirnov's test (Siegel, 1956). Kolmogorov Smirnov's test is to calculate between the sample cumulative probability function and the hypothesized distribution function in each class interval (Daniel, 1998).

CUSUM Control Chart

The CUSUM control chart was researched for the first time by Page in 1954 (Montgomery D. , 2013). This chart collects some of the previous samples to become an observation point. The CUSUM's control chart function detects the shift in the mean process from the target.

The CUSUM graph is more effective than the Shewhart graph in detecting small process mean shifts because of C_i combine information from multiple samples. In addition, the performance of the CUSUM graph is more effective with a sample size of $n = 1$ (Montgomery D. C., 2009).

There are two ways to present the CUSUM, its tabular CUSUM and V-mask CUSUM. The CUSUM tabular chart can be used on individual data (single) or subgroup data. The performance of the CUSUM control chart if the shift in the average target process which is determined is showed up, it will provide a signal and detection. The CUSUM tabular value (denoted by C_{i+} and C_{i-}) is referred to as a data depiction of one side up (+) and one side down (-) to monitor the process mean (Khosti, et al 2011).

EWMA Control Chart

Robert introduced the EWMA control chart in 1959. The EWMA control chart is quite effective for a small shift in a process. The EWMA control chart collects the previous samples to obtain plot points that later will become observed on the chart. This chart is one alternative control chart that is more sensitive to small shifts in the mean process. (Montgomery D. C., 2009).

The EWMA control chart provides weight smoothing on each sample data. Weight giving aims to give a correction on limit control and change the plot pattern so that could detect furthermore whether the process has been truly done statistically controlled or not. The selection of the most efficient weights is being done by trying to reduce the value until finding the most significant graphic pattern that provides information on the behavior of the graph pattern that is not random. (Antono, et al 2016).

Average Run Length

The performance evaluation of the control chart can be done by measuring how quickly the control graph catches the uncontrolled signal. One way is to use ARL values. ARL is the observations' average that must be described before an uncontrolled signal appears. In the Shewhart control chart, ARL is expressed by the formula $\frac{1}{\alpha}$ where α is the probability

of a type I error (states the situation is out of control even though the situation is under control) (Montgomery D. , 2013).

Based on analytical studies related to ARL performance on the CUSUM control chart, it is recommended to use $k = \frac{1}{2}$ parameter and $h = 4$ or $h = 5$ parameters. The utility of parameters with these values will provide good performance for the CUSUM control chart. And it is based on the acquisition of ARL itself at an average shift of 1σ (Khosti, et al 2011). Table 1 shows the ARL performance on the CUSUM control chart.

The smaller the ARL, the smaller the expected number of samples required until an out-of-control signal occurs. This thing means that the smaller ARL becomes, the faster the control graph detects a shift (Montgomery D. C., 2009).

Several research conducted related ARL performance on EWMA control chart. One of them is research from Lucas and Saccucci who did simulation ARL value with C program computing. The conclusion based on simulation results are EWMA control chart will perform with good if use $\lambda = 0,40$ with $L = 3,054$, $\lambda = 0,25$ with $L = 2,998$, $\lambda = 0,20$ with $L = 2,962$, $\lambda = 0,10$ with $L = 2,814$, $\lambda = 0,05$ with $L = 2,615$. Table 2 is a table that shows the obtained ARL values on EWMA control chart for the exact parameters Lucas and Saccucci (Kalgoda A. A. et al, 2011).

Table 1. ARL Performance on CUSUM Control Chart

Shifts in Mean (Multiple of σ)	$h = 4$	$h = 5$
0	168	465
0.25	74.2	139
0.5	26.6	38
0.75	13.3	17.0
1	8.38	10.4
1.5	4.75	5.75
2	3.34	4.01
2.5	2.62	3.11
3	2.19	2.57
4	1.71	2.01

Source: (Montgomery D. C., 2009)

Table 2. ARL Performance on EWMA Control Chart

Shifts in Mean (Multiple of σ)	$L = 3,054$	$L = 2,998$	$L = 2,962$	$L = 2,814$	$L = 2,615$
	$\lambda = 0,40$	$\lambda = 0,25$	$\lambda = 0,20$	$\lambda = 0,10$	$\lambda = 0,05$
0,00	500,00	500,00	500,00	500,00	500,00
0,25	224,00	170,00	150,00	106,00	84,10
0,50	71,20	48,20	41,80	31,30	28,80
0,75	28,40	20,10	18,20	15,90	16,40
1,00	14,30	11,10	10,50	10,30	11,40
1,50	5,90	5,50	5,50	6,10	7,10
2,00	3,50	3,60	3,70	4,40	5,20
2,50	2,50	2,70	2,90	3,40	4,20
3,00	2,00	2,30	2,40	2,90	3,50
4,00	1,40	1,70	1,9	2,20	2,70

Source: (Kalgoda A. A. et al, 2011)

METHOD

Flowchart Diagram

The flowchart diagram for this research can be seen in figure 1 what are you doing:

Figure 1 Flowchart Diagram

Research Approach

The approach used in this research is a quantitative approach with the help of a literature study, which is carried out by reviewing scientific works related to quantitative's research. Next, analyze the process of controlling the quality of production data using four methods, namely the Kolmogorov Smirnov Normality Test, CUSUM, EWMA, and Average Run Length.

Source Data

The utility of data in this study uses primary data that comes from production at PT XYZ. And based on the data obtained, there is one product with viscosity parameters that are often out of the spec that causes product defects, namely the Cinsperse CH-20 product. This problem will affect the increase in the stock of defective products and cause the product to have a HOLD status, which means that the product production failed. The targets of the quality at PT. XYZ is 99%, which means that defective products, must be reduced to a minimum to get good quality products. This study case is a batch system that presents the utility of a Cumulative-Sum (CUSUM) control chart and an Exponentially Weighted Moving Average (EWMA) control chart.

Kolmogorov – Smirnov Test

The Kolmogorov Smirnov test is a statistical method used to test the comparative hypothesis of two independent samples or a test used to test the null hypothesis that states that two independent samples come from identical populations in terms of location and distribution (Wahyuni Saputri, et al 2014).

Before conducting the analysis, the normality test will be carried out by using the Kolmogorov Smirnov test using two parameters, namely Viscous and Dry Matter with the following formula:

$$D_{count} = \max\{|F_0(x_i) - S(x_i)|\} \quad (1)$$

with:

- D_{count} : maximum deviation.
- $F_0(x_i)$: distribution function hypothesized to be a normal distribution.
- $S(x_i)$: cumulative distribution function from the sample data.

And the results obtained are 0.179 for Viscous D_{count} , 0,242 for Viscous D_{table} and 0.074 for Dry Matter D_{count} , 0,242 for Dry Matter D_{table} .

CUSUM Control Chart

Cumulative Sum (CUSUM) is used to detect small shifts in the mean or variance during the process due to special causes with efficient the CUSUM diagram itself directly calculates all the information in the sequence of sample values by figuring the cumulative number of deviations of the sample value from the target value. The CUSUM chart is also used as an alternative to the Shewhart control chart for the phase II monitoring process and monitors the average of the process (Arvi Fitriani, et al 2015).

On this research k and h value taken is k = 0,5 and h = 4 and can be calculated by the following formula:

$$C_i^+ = \max\{0, \bar{x}_i - (\mu_0 + K) + C_0^+\} \quad (2)$$

$$C_i^- = \min\{0, \bar{x}_i - (\mu_0 - K) + C_0^-\} \quad (3)$$

With:

C_i = total difference between the sample values and the sample target values for the i-th sample.

x_i = value of the i-th sample.

μ_0 = target value

K = allowance or slack value which is generally obtained from:

$$K = k \times \sigma \text{ Atau } K = \frac{\delta}{2} \times \sigma = \left| \frac{\mu_1 - \mu_0}{2} \right| \quad (4)$$

With:

k = constant

Some research recommend the value of k is 0,5

CUSUM control limits can be formulated following:

$$ULC = H = h \times \sigma \quad (5)$$

$$LLC = -H \quad (6)$$

With:

ULC = upper control limit

LLC = lower control limit

h = constant

σ = standard deviation

EWMA Control Chart

EWMA is a statistical method to monitor the production process. The EWMA control chart is a tool that can be used to control whether a production process is running well or not. The EWMA control chart is sensitive to small shifts in the process mean of normally distributed variables. A multivariant quality control process can be done if there is a relationship between quality variables. In addition, improving a quality variable process that connected each other with just improving one quality variable may not necessarily improve the quality of the others, so optimal repair techniques have needed for all quality variables (Arvi Fitriani, et al 2015).

To construct the EWMA control chart, it's necessary to have the value of λ and L . Value of λ which referred to the EWMA weight factor has been used to find the plot points of the EWMA, while the value of L used to determine the limit of EWMA. In this research λ and L value which is taken is $\lambda = 0,05$ and $L = 2,615$, and formula for plot point EWMA control chart is following:

$$z_i = \lambda X_i + (1 - \lambda) z_{i-1} \quad (7)$$

with:

λ = EWMA weighting parameter with value $0 < \lambda \leq 1$

Z_i = EWMA value

X_i = production data at i time

i = 1,2,3, ..., m

The control limit for the EWMA control chart are:

$$ULC = \mu_0 + L \sigma \sqrt{\frac{\lambda}{2-\lambda} [1 - (1 - \lambda) 2i]} \quad (8)$$

$$GT = \mu_0 \quad (9)$$

$$LLC = \mu_0 - L \sigma \sqrt{\frac{\lambda}{2-\lambda} [1 - (1 - \lambda) 2i]} \quad (10)$$

With:

L = Width of control limit

σ = Standard deviation

The process is under control if Z_i is between ULC and LLC.

Average Run Length

Average Run Length (ARL) is the average number of samples (subgroups) that must be observed until the first out-of-control is found. For ARL_1 (ARL is in an uncontrolled state) then the value of $p = 1 - \beta =$ failure probability or type-II error (declare a controlled state or the probability that a sample mean point falls within the control limits when the process is out of control) (Darmanto, 2012).

To get the ARL value can be done by approaching it using the interpolation formula with the following equation:

$$A = A_0 + \frac{(A_1 - A_0)}{(B_1 - B_0)} (B - B_0) \quad (11)$$

If $\Delta\mu$ is the deviation of the change in mean value due to a shift in the target, with a standard deviation of, then the magnitude of the shifts in the mean process in standard deviation units can be calculated by the formula (Montgomery D., 2013) :

$$\delta = \frac{\Delta\mu}{\sigma}, \text{ with } \sigma \neq 0$$

Analysis of Observation Results

The technique used to solve the problem in this research is statistical quality control with the application of CUSUM and EWMA control charts. What is compared from the two charts is the sensitivity to get a control chart that is more sensitive for small shifts.

Comparison for CUSUM and EWMA chart performance based on the ability of each control chart to detect any instability (out of control) at the same time process so that the ARL value obtain for each control chart. The control chart that produces the smallest ARL is a more effective control chart in detecting the mean shift in each process that affects the quality of the resulting product.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Kolmogorov-Smirnov Normality Test

Before analyzing CUSUM and EWMA control chart, a normality test will be performed first on the Cinsperse CH-20 production data with viscosity and dry matter parameters. The carried out tests by using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test with the results in table 4.

Table 3. Kolmogorov-Smirnov Normality Test Result

	D_{count}	D_{table}
Viscous	0.179	0.242
Dry Matter	0.074	0.242

Based on Table 3, the two parameters that viscosity and dry matter have a value of $D_{count} < D_{table}$, so H_0 is accepted, which means the data on the amount of Cinsperse CH-20 production meets the normals distribution assumption. Because the production data meet the normals distribution assumption, the production data can be analyzed further using CUSUM and EWMA control charts.

CUSUM Control Chart

The CUSUM control chart used is tabular CUSUM. To construct a CUSUM control graph, the first step to do is to define the k and h parameters to reach the control limits and CUSUM plot points. In the research had been done by (Montgomery D., 2013), the recommended value is $h = 4$ or $h = 5$ and $k = 0,5$ value will generally give good performance to ARL at a shift of 1σ in the process mean. On this research k and h value which taken is $k = 0,5$ and $h = 4$, for $k = 5$ parameters used according to the recommendations of previous studies while for $h = 4$ parameters it is used because it has a smaller result at the upper control limit and the lower control limit CUSUM so that the detected shift will be more accurate because the upper control limit and lower control limit are small. The following results of the CUSUM calculation from the production of Cinsperse CH-20 with two parameters, Viscous and Dry Matter, can be seen in table 4.

Table 4 CUSUM Calculation Results on Cinsperse CH-20 Production

Sample	Viscous				Dry Matter			
	C+	C-	ULC	LLC	C+	C-	ULC	LLC
1	624.13	0.00	3806.93	-3806.93	0.00	0.00	1.80	-1.80
2	0.00	-374.13	3806.93	-3806.93	0.00	0.00	1.80	-1.80

3	0.00	-1818.27	3806.93	-3806.93	0.00	-0.17	1.80	-1.80
4	0.00	-2642.40	3806.93	-3806.93	0.00	0.00	1.80	-1.80
5	0.00	-3466.53	3806.93	-3806.93	0.00	-0.36	1.80	-1.80
6	0.00	-4290.67	3806.93	-3806.93	0.00	-0.71	1.80	-1.80
7	0.00	-3464.80	3806.93	-3806.93	0.00	-0.37	1.80	-1.80
8	1324.13	-1188.93	3806.93	-3806.93	0.00	-0.59	1.80	-1.80
9	648.27	-913.07	3806.93	-3806.93	0.00	-0.24	1.80	-1.80
10	0.00	-1437.20	3806.93	-3806.93	0.00	-0.52	1.80	-1.80
11	0.00	-1811.33	3806.93	-3806.93	0.00	-0.16	1.80	-1.80
12	0.00	-1705.47	3806.93	-3806.93	0.68	0.00	1.80	-1.80
13	0.00	-2259.60	3806.93	-3806.93	0.00	-0.62	1.80	-1.80
14	804.13	-503.73	3806.93	-3806.93	0.00	-0.80	1.80	-1.80
15	1348.27	0.00	3806.93	-3806.93	0.00	-0.84	1.80	-1.80
16	0.00	-404.13	3806.93	-3806.93	0.59	0.00	1.80	-1.80
17	0.00	-388.27	3806.93	-3806.93	0.00	-0.43	1.80	-1.80
18	0.00	0.00	3806.93	-3806.93	0.00	-0.29	1.80	-1.80
19	0.00	-224.13	3806.93	-3806.93	0.00	-0.16	1.80	-1.80
20	0.00	-188.27	3806.93	-3806.93	0.00	-0.18	1.80	-1.80
21	0.00	-912.40	3806.93	-3806.93	0.00	-0.71	1.80	-1.80
22	0.00	-1256.53	3806.93	-3806.93	0.00	-1.28	1.80	-1.80
23	414.13	0.00	3806.93	-3806.93	0.00	-1.41	1.80	-1.80
24	0.00	-424.13	3806.93	-3806.93	0.00	-1.19	1.80	-1.80
25	974.13	0.00	3806.93	-3806.93	0.00	-1.05	1.80	-1.80
26	178.27	0.00	3806.93	-3806.93	0.12	-0.48	1.80	-1.80
27	0.00	0.00	3806.93	-3806.93	0.00	-0.45	1.80	-1.80
28	0.00	-474.13	3806.93	-3806.93	0.07	0.00	1.80	-1.80
29	0.00	-1198.27	3806.93	-3806.93	0.41	0.00	1.80	-1.80
30	0.00	-1622.40	3806.93	-3806.93	0.38	0.00	1.80	-1.80
σ	951.7331				0.4500			
μ_0	3500				20			
Mean	3122				19.88			
K	475.8665				0.2250			

Based on table 4, the CUSUM control chart is shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3.

Figure 2 Viscous's CUSUM Control Chart

Figure 3 Dry Matter's CUSUM Control Chart

EWMA Control Chart

The first step to creating an EWMA control chart is to define EWMA z_0 early value. Similar to CUSUM, on EWMA control chart z_0 early value can be obtained in two ways which are by calculating the average or by using the target value that has been applied by the company. To compile the EWMA control chart, λ and L values are needed. The λ value called the EWMA weight factor is used to find EWMA plot points, while the L value is used to determine the EWMA boundary. In the research conducted (Saccucci, et al 1990), the λ and L value taken are $\lambda = 0,40$ with $L = 3.054$, $\lambda = 0,25$ with $L = 2,998$, $\lambda = 0,20$ with $L = 2,962$, $\lambda = 0,10$ with $L = 2,814$, $\lambda = 0,05$ with $L = 2,615$. In this research λ and L values taken are $\lambda = 0,05$ and $L = 2,615$ because the λ and L values provide a more sensitive control chart. The weighting value of $\lambda = 0,05$ has taken because λ value affects the EWMA control chart in detecting small mean shifts. If λ value is getting smaller, then z_i value will be getting bigger, the λ value on the EWMA control chart is getting smaller the more effective it will be on detecting small mean shifts, and $L = 2,615$ used because it has smaller results on EWMA upper control limit and lower control limit so that the detected shift will be more accurate because of the upper control limit and lower control limit. (Nelwati, et al, 2015).

The following are the results of the EWMA calculation from the production of Cinsperse CH-20 with two parameters is Viscous and Dry Matter is shown in table 5.

Table 5 EWMA Calculation Results on Cinsperse CH-20 production

Sample	Viscous				Dry Matter			
	Zi	ULC	LLC	GT	Zi	ULC	LLC	GT
1	3555.00	3624.44	3375.56	3500	20.00	20.06	19.94	20.00
2	3509.75	3671.64	3328.36	3500	20.01	20.08	19.92	20.00
3	3413.26	3705.12	3294.88	3500	19.99	20.10	19.90	20.00
4	3352.60	3731.21	3268.79	3500	20.00	20.11	19.89	20.00
5	3294.97	3752.45	3247.55	3500	19.97	20.12	19.88	20.00
6	3240.22	3770.19	3229.81	3500	19.94	20.13	19.87	20.00
7	3270.71	3785.25	3214.75	3500	19.95	20.13	19.87	20.00
8	3372.17	3798.19	3201.81	3500	19.93	20.14	19.86	20.00
9	3368.57	3809.41	3190.59	3500	19.94	20.15	19.85	20.00
10	3325.14	3819.20	3180.80	3500	19.92	20.15	19.85	20.00
11	3291.38	3827.78	3172.22	3500	19.93	20.15	19.85	20.00
12	3283.31	3835.33	3164.67	3500	19.98	20.16	19.84	20.00
13	3242.65	3842.01	3157.99	3500	19.93	20.16	19.84	20.00
14	3319.51	3847.92	3152.08	3500	19.92	20.16	19.84	20.00
15	3379.54	3853.17	3146.83	3500	19.91	20.17	19.83	20.00
16	3341.56	3857.85	3142.15	3500	19.95	20.17	19.83	20.00
17	3326.48	3862.02	3137.98	3500	19.92	20.17	19.83	20.00
18	3335.66	3865.74	3134.26	3500	19.92	20.17	19.83	20.00
19	3308.88	3869.06	3130.94	3500	19.92	20.17	19.83	20.00
20	3296.43	3872.04	3127.96	3500	19.91	20.18	19.82	20.00
21	3246.61	3874.70	3125.30	3500	19.88	20.18	19.82	20.00
22	3218.28	3877.09	3122.91	3500	19.85	20.18	19.82	20.00
23	3276.87	3879.23	3120.77	3500	19.84	20.18	19.82	20.00
24	3243.02	3881.16	3118.84	3500	19.84	20.18	19.82	20.00
25	3328.37	3882.88	3117.12	3500	19.85	20.18	19.82	20.00
26	3320.95	3884.44	3115.56	3500	19.87	20.18	19.82	20.00
27	3312.41	3885.83	3114.17	3500	19.87	20.18	19.82	20.00
28	3274.29	3887.09	3112.91	3500	19.89	20.18	19.82	20.00
29	3225.57	3888.22	3111.78	3500	19.92	20.18	19.82	20.00
30	3194.29	3889.24	3110.76	3500	19.94	20.18	19.82	20.00
σ	951.7331				0.4500			
L	2.615				2.615			
Mean	3122				19.88			
λ	0.05				0.05			

Based on table 5, the EWMA control chart following is:

Figure 4 Viscous’s EWMA Control Chart

Figure 5 Dry Matter’s EWMA Control Chart

In Figure 4, there is one plot that exceeds LLC, it is the 6th plot. With the plot that is out of the control limit, the Cinsperse CH-20 production process can be said to be statistically uncontrolled. While in Figure 5, there is no plot that is out of the control limit, the Cinsperse CH-20 production process can be said to be statistically uncontrolled.

Average Run Length (ARL)

After analyzing CUSUM and EWMA control charts, the analysis continued by calculating the ARL value for both the parameters and the control charts. Both parameters have standard deviation values that are not equal to 0 so that the mean shift can be calculated by equation (11).

If the calculation results do not contain ARL values as in table 1 and table 2. Then to get the ARL value, a value approach is carried out using the interpolation formula with equation (12).

Table 6 ARL Calculation Result on Viscous and Dry Matter

	μ_0	μ_1	σ	Δ	ARL CUSUM	ARL EWMA
Viscous	3500	3122	951.7331	0.3972	79.5432	51.5460
Dry Matter	20	19.8837	0.4500	0.2585	135.5638	82.2186

From table 6, it’s known that the ARL value of the control chart for the viscosity parameter is 79,542 for CUSUM and 51,5460 for EWMA, while for the dry matter parameter, the result is 135,5638 for CUSUM and 82,2186 for EWMA. From the ARL results, both the viscosity and dry matter parameters, the EWMA control chart shows smaller results than CUSUM. The smaller ARL value obtained from both parameters determines that the EWMA control chart is more sensitive than the CUSUM control chart. It’s shown on the EWMA control chart that the plot that goes out of control limit is more than the CUSUM control chart, meaning that the EWMA control chart detects a relatively small average shift faster, so in the CH-20 Cinsperse production process at PT. XYZ will affect the production quality results.

CONCLUSION

Based on control chart analysis that uses two parameters, viscosity and dry matter with $k = 0.5$ and $h = 4$ value for the CUSUM control chart and $\lambda = 0.05$ and $L = 2.615$ value for the EWMA control chart. It’s shown that on the Cinsperse CH-20 production process, the viscosity parameter is statistically uncontrolled because there is one plot below the LLC

value, on the CUSUM control chart and the EWMA control chart the 6th data plot. Meanwhile, both on CUSUM and EWMA control charts, the Cinsperse CH-20 production process on dry matter parameters have statistically controlled because there were no plots outside ULC and LLC.

To overcome the statistically uncontrolled parameter because there is one plot below the LLC value, it is necessary to improve the Cinsperse CH-20 production process. Because the monomer and catalyst dosing process is a main critical process to determine viscosity, the improvement to get the appropriate viscosities is by always paying attention to the quality of the raw material monomer and catalyst used in Cinsperse CH-20 production, the monomer and catalyst dosing process still done manually it allows failures to occur due to human error, therefore, it is necessary to train operators to always work according to the applicable standard operating procedures (SOP) and always perform preventive maintenance on machines that used so that the accuracy of the temperature, pressure and reaction rates in the monomer and catalyst dosing process is following the actual.

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